

Influence of Temperature on the Setting of Inorganic Jellies.

By SATYA PRAKASH.

In previous publications from this laboratory (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 391, 587; *ibid*, 1930, **7**, 367, 417, 591; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, **201**, 301.) we have investigated the preparation and properties of a number of inorganic jellies. We have also studied (*J. Phys. Chem.* 1930, **34**, 954) the influence of temperature on the coagulation of various sols and have shown that such sols as hydrous oxides of iron, chromium, tin and aluminium become comparatively unstable when the temperature is raised, whilst easily hydrolysable sols such as prussian blue, gamboge and mastic are stabilised at higher temperatures.

In this communication, we are recording our observations on the influence of temperature on the setting of various jellies. The jelly-forming mixtures were prepared at ordinary temperatures and divided into three portions, and they were allowed to set in thermostats maintained at three different temperatures. The time of setting of the jellies was noted in every case. The setting point of a jelly was sharp enough to take readings with an accuracy of 10 seconds.

The jellies were prepared by methods described in foregoing papers. Where the jellies were obtained by coagulation, the sols were dialysed for such periods as were necessary to produce jellies of the best texture. So long as the sols were comparatively impure, either no jelles were formed or they gave loose opaque coagulum. In no case the sols could be completely freed from electrolytic impurities, as there was an apprehension of the spontaneous setting of sols to jellies by dialysis alone.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Zirconium Hydroxide Jelly.

The jelly was prepared by the addition of various quantities of 3·84*N*-sodium acetate to 3 c. c. of 10% zirconium nitrate

solution, and the volume was made up to 5 c. c. in every case. The mixtures were allowed to set at 30°, 50° and 70°. The results are recorded in the following table.

TABLE I.

0.348N-sodium acetate	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
0.1 c. c.	No jelly	No jelly	No jelly.
0.2	Do	Do	Do
0.3	Do	Do	Do
0.4	3 hrs.	6 mins.	35 sec.
0.5	2 mins.	30 secs.	Immediately.

The results recorded in this table show that below a certain minimum concentration of sodium acetate, no jelly is formed even at higher temperatures. The time of setting of the jelly is markedly decreased at higher temperatures.

Zirconium Borate Jelly.

The jelly was prepared by dialysing for four days the sol obtained by mixing saturated borax solution with 10% zirconium nitrate solution and coagulating the sol by different amounts of $N/5$ potassium sulphate.

Concentration of the sol = 24.72 g. zirconium borate per litre.
Amount of sol taken = 3 c. c. Total volume = 5 c. c.

TABLE II.

$N/5-K_2SO_4$	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
0.4 c. c.	2 hrs.	30 mins.	15 mins.
0.5	16 min.	12	5
0.6	13	11	1
0.7	No jelly but ppt.	4	30 sec.
0.8	No jelly but ppt.	No jelly but ppt.	20 sec. the jelly soon synerises.

Zirconium Molybdate Jelly.

The sol of zirconium molybdate was prepared by mixing 3% potassium molybdate solution with 10% zirconium nitrate solution and dialysing the mixture for 5 days. Concentration of the sol was 14.48 g. zirconium molybdate per litre. The jellies were prepared by coagulating the sol with different amounts of *N/50* potassium sulphate.

Amount of sol taken = 10 c. c. Total volume = 12 c. c.

TABLE III.

<i>N/50-K₂SO₄</i>	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
1.2 c. c.	No jelly	2 hrs. 30 min.	10 min.
1.3	5 hrs.	1 hr. 20 min.	6
1.4	3 hrs. 15 min.	1 hr.	6
1.5	1 hr. 25 min.	29 min.	4
1.6	45 min.	22 min.	2

Thorium Arsenate Jelly.

This jelly was obtained by mixing different concentrations of 18% potassium arsenate solution with 10 c. c. of thorium nitrate (12.06 g. of the salt per litre), the solution being made up to 12 c.c. in every case.

TABLE IV.

18% KH_2SO_4 .	Time of setting.		
	30°	40°	45°
0.7 c. c.	1 day	No jelly	No jelly
0.8	2 hrs.	Do	Do
0.9	25 min.	Loose jelly in 2½ hrs.	Do
1.0	18	35 min.	2 hrs.
1.1	5	26 min.	90 min.

When the temperature was raised above 50°, the thorium arsenate mixture did not yield any jelly, not even when kept for

five hours. However, if the jelly-forming mixtures be again brought to 30°, they set to jellies.

Thorium Phosphate Jelly.

The jellies of thorium phosphate were prepared by adding varying amounts of 11% potassium phosphate solution to 10 c. c. of thorium nitrate solution (12.06 g. per litre). The total volume was made up to 12 c. c. in every case.

TABLE V.

11% KH_2PO_4 .	Time of setting.		
	30°	40°	45°
0.8 c. c.	No jelly	No jelly	No jelly
0.9	120 min.	66 min.	58 min.
1.0	48	24	20
1.1	16	10	7
1.2	2	2	2

Thorium Molybdate Jelly.

These jellies were prepared by adding varying amounts of 4.5% potassium molybdate to 10 c. c. of thorium nitrate solution containing 12.06 g. of the salt per 250 c. c.

Total volume = 12 c. c.

TABLE VI.

4.5% K_2MoO_4 .	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
0.9 c. c.	> 60 min.	30 min.	22 min.
1.0	> 60	25	16
1.1	33	20	11
1.2	30	18	10
1.3	28	15	8

Chromium Arsenate Jelly.

The sol was prepared by dialysing the mixture of 100 c. c. of $M/2$ -chromic chloride and 80 c. c. of 18% potassium arsenate

solution for 6 days. It set to jellies when coagulated with $N/5$ potassium sulphate.

TABLE VII.

Concentration of the sol = 36.4 g. per litre.
Amount of sol taken = 10 c. c. Total volume = 15 c. c.

$N/5-K_2SO_4$	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
2.2 c. c.	54 min.	10 min.	1 min.
2.3	36	4	1
2.4	22	3	50 sec.
2.5	15	2	30 sec.
2.6	Ppt.	Ppt.	Ppt.

Vanadium Pentoxide Jelly.

Vanadic acid was precipitated by adding concentrated hydrochloric acid to ammonium vanadate. The precipitate on careful washing passed into a clear red sol, which set to jellies when coagulated with potassium chloride. Concentration of the sol was 1.92 g. vanadium pentoxide per litre.

Amount of sol taken = 5 c. c. Total volume = 12 c.c.

TABLE VIII.

$N/20-KCl$	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
1.0 c.c.	3 hrs. 20 min.	No jelly in 3 hrs.	No jelly in 3 hrs.
1.2	38 min.	No jelly in 3 hrs	No jelly
1.3	20	100 min.	Do
1.4	13	45	Do
1.5	4	30	150 min.

Mercuri-sulphosalicylic Acid Jelly.

Mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid was prepared by dissolving 1.5 mols of mercuric oxide in 1 mol. of sulphosalicylic acid and drying the mixture on a water-bath. One gram of the powder thus obtained

was dissolved in 100 c. c. of water. A clear sol with slight opalescence was obtained which set to jellies on addition of $N\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$.

8 c. c. of 1% mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid were taken every time and the total volume was made up to 10 c. c.

TABLE IX.

$N\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$.	Time of setting.		
	30°	40°	50°
0.4	No jelly	No jelly	No jelly
0.5	18 min.	Do	Do
0.6	10	30 min.	Do
0.7	7	15	Do
1.0	1	2	Loose jelly in 8 min.

Zinc Arsenate Jelly.

Zinc arsenate jellies were prepared by taking 5 c. c. of zinc sulphate solution (14.868 g. in 250 c. c.) and adding an equal quantity of water to it and then mixing it with different amounts of 18% potassium arsenate solution. The the total volume was made up to 20 c. c. in every case.

TABLE X.

18% KH_2AsO_4 .	Time of setting.		
	30°	50°	70°
0.16	Did not set	Loose jelly in 60 sec.	Ppt.
0.18	„	90 sec.	30 sec.
0.20	„	60	5
0.30	5 sec.	5	5

Stannic Arsenate Jelly.

To 2 or 3 c.c. of $M/1.099$ -stannic chloride solution were added the varying concentrations of 18% potassium arsenate solution and the total volume was made up to 6 c.c. in every case. A set of the mixture was allowed to set at 20° while the other set was warmed for 5 minutes at 90° and then transferred to ordinary room temperature (20°). The time of gelation was noted in every case.

TABLE XI.

<i>M</i> /1'099-Stannic chloride.	18% Potassium arsenate.	Time of setting.	
		20°	90° (warming)
3·0 c.c.	1 c.c.	23 hrs.	10 hrs.
3·0	2	90 min.	6 min.
3·0	3	25 min.	3
2·0	0·5	24 hrs.	5

The marked temperature influence observed in the case of this substance is probably due to the fact that warming for a few minutes at a higher temperature causes the hydrolysis of stannic arsenate to stannic oxide. The oxide is also known to yield fine jellies which under the circumstances may set more rapidly than the arsenate jelly.

Stannic Phosphate Jelly.

3 C.c. of *M*/1'099-stannic chloride solution were mixed with varying amounts of 22 per cent. potassium phosphate solution and the total volume was made up to 6 c.c. in every case. One set of the mixture was allowed to set at 20° while the other at 90°.

TABLE XII.

22% KH_2PO_4 .	Time of setting.	
	20°	90°
0·5 c.c.	22 hrs.	5 min.
1·0	2 hrs.	3
1·5	30 min.	2
2·0	18	1

Stannic Tungstate Jelly.

1·5 or 2 c.c. of 1·53*M* stannic chloride solution were mixed with different concentrations of 15% sodium tungstate solution. The total volume was made up to 6 c.c. in every case. The mixtures were shaken for five minutes and then transferred to baths at 20° and 93° and the time of gelation was observed.

TABLE XIII.

1.58M-Stannic chloride.	15% Sodium tungstate.	Time of setting	
		20°	93°
2 c.c.	2.0 c.c.	No jelly	No jelly
2	2.5	No jelly	20 min.
2	3.0	5 days	8
2	3.5	2 days	6
1.5	2.0	>5 hrs.	8

Stannic Molybdate Jelly.

A mixture of stannic chloride in excess and potassium molybdate was dialysed for 24 hours. Concentration of the sol was 91.04 g. SnO₂ per litre. This sol when half diluted gave jellies at different temperatures as follows:

TABLE XIV.

Temp.	...	90°	70°	60°	50°	40°	34°
Time of gelation in min.	...	1	2	4	7	20	360.

Discussion.

The results recorded in the foregoing tables show that in the case of zirconium hydroxide, zirconium molybdate, zirconium borate, thorium molybdate, thorium phosphate, chromium tungstate, stannic arsenate, phosphate, tungstate and molybdate, the time of setting markedly decreases as the temperature is raised.

The jellies of thorium arsenate, vanadium pentoxide and mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid take a longer time to set at higher temperatures, and above a certain temperature, they do not set at all.

No systematic work appears to have been done before on the influence of temperature on the formation of jellies. Fleming (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1902, **41**, 427) and Holmes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, **22**, 516) observed that a slight increase in temperature accelerates the time of setting of silicic acid jelly, while Fells and Firth (*ibid.*, 1925, **29**, 248) did not observe any distinct variation with temperature over the range from 0° to 45°. Conflicting results are also found in the case of manganous arsenate jellies (*cf.* Deiss, *Kolloid. Z.*, 1914, **14**, 139; and Kraemer, *Colloid Symp. Monograph*, Wisconsin, 1923, **1**, 66). We have observed that if the manganous chloride and potassium arsenate mixture is warmed at 60° to 80°, it will form manganous

arsenate jelly more conveniently than if the mixture is allowed to remain at ordinary temperature.

Bunce (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1914, 18, 269) observed that a slight increase in the temperature accelerates the gelation of mercuric oxide jellies but heating for five minutes above 63° seems to prevent the formation of the jelly. Szegvari and Schalek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 32, 318; *ibid.*, 33, 326) observed in the case of iron oxide jelly that the setting time decreases with the rise in temperature.

In the case of organic jellies, like gelatin, agar agar, soap, starch, pectin and others, the behaviour is quite different. The lowering of temperature always favours their gelation. These jellies also undergo a sort of melting when temperature is raised and the melted sol again assumes the jelly form when cooled, and thus, these jellies are heat reversible. Most of the inorganic jellies do not show this sort of reversibility.

The change in temperature in case of jelly-forming mixtures causes the variation in the solubility of the dispersed phase, in the degree of hydrolysis, in the hydration of particles and in the rate of coagulation. The setting time appears to be a complicated function of all these factors. Organic substances, due to the marked temperature influence on the solubility, form both true and colloidal solutions, and at different temperatures an equilibrium exists between the molecules and colloidal aggregates. As the temperature is lowered, due to the decrease in solubility, the colloidal phase begins to preponderate, which on developing surficial and structural hydration under suitable conditions, sets to a jelly.

With the exception of those inorganic sols which appear to undergo marked hydrolysis with rise in temperature, the rate of coagulation is markedly increased if the temperature is raised and with the rapid decrease in charge, the viscosity and hydration of particles also increase. Thus a jelly is obtained in a comparatively shorter time at higher temperatures. The sols undergoing hydrolysis at higher temperatures become stable towards coagulation and as such, the jelly takes more time to set. The agglomeration tendency of the particles also appears to be favoured at higher temperatures and consequently, the jellies obtained at higher temperatures are more opalescent.

In the case of polybasic salts of heavy metals, like tin, zirconium, thorium and others, it is highly probable that as the temperature increases, they are hydrolysed and hydrous oxides are formed. In

case of such substances, the hydrous oxides also have a tendency of developing hydration, and some times greater than the corresponding polybasic salts. In such cases of mixed jellies, the time of setting would depend upon the hydration developed by different phases.

The jelly of mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid resembles more or less the organic jellies, whose setting is favoured by the lowering of temperature. It appears that the anomalous thorium arsenate and vanadium pentoxide jellies exhibit when freshly formed what is known as the 'melting of jellies,' a phenomenon so common in the case of organic jellies. It has been found that though a jelly-forming mixture of thorium arsenate remains liquified at 60°, the jelly of the same concentration prepared at ordinary temperature, but allowed to age for some hours does not undergo melting if the temperature is raised. A similar observation has been made in the case of vanadium pentoxide. This appears to be partly due to the decrease in the hydration tendency and partly to the decrease in the surface energy on ageing. This effect is not so marked in the case of organic jellies which are, consequently heat reversible.

Summary.

1. The influence of temperature on the setting of various inorganic jellies has been investigated. It has been observed that all the inorganic jellies with the exception of thorium arsenate, vanadium pentoxide and mercuri-sulphosalicylic acid, set more readily at higher temperatures than at low. The jellies (these three exceptions) are not formed above 60°.

2. In the case of such inorganic sols which do not undergo hydrolysis, the rise in temperature increases the rate of coagulation, and consequently, the hydration is more rapidly developed and the jellies are readily obtained.

3. The jellies of polybasic salts are hydrolysed at higher temperatures to the corresponding hydroxides which have also a tendency to form jellies, and hence the setting time would depend upon the tendency of mixed phases.

4. The jellies of vanadium pentoxide and thorium arsenate show the 'melting phenomenon' at higher temperatures.

In conclusion, the author wishes to express his indebtedness to Prof. N. R. Dhar for his very kind interest and guidance in this work.